

STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF MODIFIED GRAPHENE/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Graphene, a two-dimensional material known as “the thinnest material in the universe and the strongest ever measured” [1], possesses high specific surface area (2630 m²/g) [2], thermal conductivity [3], flexibility and mechanical strength (130 GPa) [4]. To fully exploit these remarkable properties, graphene can be use into polymer matrices as nanofillers [5]. As for graphene-based nanocomposites, an essential criterion about performance of the resulting composites is required, which including delicate morphological organization, local interfacial properties, uniform dispersion, and ease of processing and so on [6-8]. These aspects mainly depend on the surface properties of graphene, which can be chemically modified for specific purposes [9]. Although significant progress have been made in the use of graphene as reinforcements of polymer matrices [10-23], there are still some critical issues unresolved such as the aggregative trend of graphene during processing and poor interfacial bonding between polymer matrices and graphene [24]. Stankovich prepare isocyanate modified graphene oxide to obtain a series products with different CPN ratio, which can form stable colloid systems in polar non-protic solvents (DMF, NMP, DMSO, HMPA and THF) [25]. Recently, the aryl diazonium treatment has been applied to graphene surface modification, achieving by grafting aryl groups on surface of graphene. This method can bind nanofillers to polymer matrices as an efficient approach. Sodium dodecylbenzene sulfonate (SDBS) wrapped graphene which grafted halogen groups has greatly improved the dispersibility of graphene in polar solvents [26]. Moreover, a graphene/polystyrene (PS) composite was obtained by combining a diazonium addition reaction with atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP). This composite reveal a 15 °C increase in the glass transition temperature (T_g), and exhibited ~70% and

57% increases in tensile strength and Young’s modulus, respectively [14]. It is proved that substituted aryl groups can be readily anchored to surface of graphene by electrochemical reaction of diazonium salts [27-32]. Notwithstanding there are a lot of studies showing that graphene can enhance tensile strength and modulus of most polymer nanocomposites more effectively than other carbon materials did [33-35], few studies have focused on developing the toughness of resin matrix.

In our recent work, we prepared a phenyl isocyanate modified graphene by covalent chemical modification of graphene oxide (GO) and tested notched impact strength of phenyl isocyanate modified graphene (PMG)/epoxy and GO/epoxy nanocomposites. Moreover, we observed the morphology of fracture surface to study the mechanism of toughening. The results illustrate that adding GO can distinctly enhance epoxy with a maximum increase of 100% in impact strength at wt 0.4%. This effect should attribute to the interaction between modified graphene and polymer matrix and provide further understanding of the reinforcing mechanism of graphene nanocomposites.

2 Experimental

2.1 Synthesis of GO

Modified Hummer’s method was applied to prepare graphite oxide from natural graphite powder, through oxidization process by potassium nitrate and potassium permanganate, in the presence of sulfuric acid [36]. This part of experiment base on the previous studies of our group, which indicated that moderately extending reaction time and raising reaction temperature slightly lead to a complete oxidation [37]. When oxidation was completed, the obtained suspension was intensively washed with deionized water by centrifugation and then followed by vacuum drying (80 °C) to obtain graphite oxide

powder. The resulting graphite oxide was exfoliated to GO by sonication in de-ionized water (DI water).

2.2 Synthesis of PMG

0.08 g GO was dispersed in THF and sonicated to obtain homogeneous colloidal solution. Subsequently, 0.008 mol phenyl isocyanate was added into mixture at 80 °C for 12 hours.

2.3 Fabrication of Epoxy Matrix Nanocomposites

GO (content ratio to resin of 0.2 wt.%, 0.4wt.% and 0.6 wt.% respectively) was dispersed well in Epon862 (31.65g) with the help of THF at 80 °C, after THF was evaporated completely by vacuum distillation (-0.1 MPa) the curing agent (8.35g) was added to the mixture which was then poured into the mould (80mm ×10mm× 8mm). The resin was degassed at 80 °C and then cured at 120 °C for 2 hours, 140 °C for 1 hour, 160 °C for 1 hour and 180 °C for 2 hours.

However, the procedure of adding resin and curing agent was different in the process of preparing PMG/epoxy nanocomposites. Right after the chemical modification was finished, the Epon862 (31.65g) is added to the PMG/THF solution firstly. Then the mixture was degassed by vacuum distillation (-0.1 MPa) after stirred until it is evenly under 80 °C. When the THF solution was absolutely evaporated, the curing agent (8.35g) was added to the mixture under 80 °C to complete the same curing process as GO/epoxy.

2.4 Instrumentation

Field emitting scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) was performed with a SUPRA 55VP microscope. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was conducted with PHI Quantera SXM system. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were obtained by a Dimension3100v in tapping mode. And Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on a Nexus 670 spectrometer, in the range of 500-4000 cm⁻¹. Impact strength of each composite specimen was tested by izod notched impact strength testing on a XJ-Z50 impact testing machine according to ISO180:2000 standard. The glass transition temperature (*T_g*) of each specimen of composites was tested by dynamic thermomechanical analysis (DMA) on DMTA IV testing machine according to ASTM D7028-07e1.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Exfoliation of GO in water and THF

Functionalization of graphene based on exfoliation of graphite oxide, which is suitable for large scale production required by polymer composite applications [9]. Graphene oxide (GO) is widely used as a precursor for mass production of graphene and its derivatives, which possesses hydroxyl and epoxide groups attached on the basal plane, and carboxyl groups at the edge [1, 4, 38-40]. To characterize the nanoplatelets in height dimension, AFM provides a reliable measure of the thickness and size of the graphene sheets. GO sheets with the thickness ranging from 0.8-1 nm are observed in Fig. 1, either GO was dispersed in water or in THF. Graphite oxide was successfully exfoliated into single-layer GO sheet after ultrasonic exfoliation. Comparing Fig. 1a with b, we can also learn that the GO sheets in water with a diameter of ~5 μm, which is much larger than that in THF (~1 μm). According to lots of hydroxyl groups and carboxyl group on GO sheets and fragmentation caused by sonication, it is much easier for GO to disperse and remain stable in larger pieces in water.

3.2 Characterization of GO and PMG

To characterize the chemical groups on the surface of GO and PMG, FT-IR experiments provide a reliable measure and the results are shown in Fig. 2. The spectrum of graphite oxide (Fig. 2a) confirms the presence of C-O (ν_{C-O} at 1050 cm⁻¹), O-C-O (ν_{O-C-O} at 1220 cm⁻¹), carboxyl C=O ($\nu_{C=O}$ at 1720 cm⁻¹) and ketene C=O ($\nu_{C=O}$ at 1620 cm⁻¹), the peak at 3370 cm⁻¹ is corresponding to the O-H stretching vibrations of the C-OH groups and the water molecules intercalated into GO [41]. When it comes to the broadening effect (ranging from 3500 to 2000 cm⁻¹), hydrogen bonds between hydroxyl groups and carboxyl groups contribute, probably. In Fig. 2b, the broaden peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ is severely attenuated and a weak peak corresponding to secondary amino groups occurs at 3300 cm⁻¹ indicating that hydroxyl groups have been consumed by isocyanate groups during modification. The IR spectrum of PMG can be also distinguished from GO as evidenced by the increasing intensity of skeleton vibration of benzene ring (1650, 1550 and 752 cm⁻¹) [42-44] and the presence of new peak at 1320 cm⁻¹, which attributed to the stretching vibration of C-N from aniline groups.

The functionalization of GO were also confirmed by XPS. The results of GO and PMG are shown in Table 1. Compared with pristine graphite, GO has an approximate C/O atomic ratio of 3/1 after a complete oxidation. The atomic percentage of O in

180 GO is also a reference to determine the mol ratio of
GO/Phenyl isocyanate in following chemical
modification. Besides, the O/N atomic ratio of PMG
is about 2/1, indicating that the hydroxyl groups on
the GO and phenyl isocyanate attained complete
185 reaction. The results confirmed that each hydroxyl
group on the surface of GO has been linked with an
isocyanate group.

3.3 Mechanical properties of GO/epoxy and PMG/epoxy nanocomposites

190 The studies focusing on mechanical properties of
GO/epoxy nanocomposite revealed an increase in
Izod notched impact strength (IS) as a function of
loading fraction. As shown in Table 2, the Izod
245 impact strength increases twice by adding GO to
epoxy resin at extremely low filler loading, but the
IS of PMG/epoxy decreases by 20%-30%.
200 Compared to the neat epoxy resin, a small addition
of GO can obviously improve the IS of GO/epoxy
nanocomposite, the IS reaches the maximum value
of 3.50 KJ/m² at 0.4 wt% GO. Then the IS of
GO/epoxy nanocomposite decreases with an
205 increase in GO loading, which is considered that
uneven distribution and agglomeration of GO make
it easy to form stress concentrations when GO
loading increased to a certain extent. We
210 investigated the morphology of the fracture surfaces
of GO/epoxy and PMG/epoxy nanocomposites using
SEM. The fracture surfaces exhibited dispersion and
215 compatibility of GO and PMG in the matrix, as
shown in Fig. 3. The fractured surface of neat epoxy
resin is quite smooth, exhibiting a typical brittle
feature (Fig. 3a). And there are two regions with
distinct pattern on the fracture surface of neat resin.
220 One, near the point of impact (region i in Fig. 3a), is
quite smooth, while the other, almost the rest of the
fracture surface (region ii in Fig. 3a), is river-like.
On the surface of GO/epoxy at the loading of 0.2%,
smooth region can also be observed. However, when
225 the percentage of GO is higher than 0.2%, we can
only find river-like pattern of denser crazes with no
smooth region on the fracture surface. While that of
the GO/epoxy nanocomposite is indented and
consists of many ductile sunken areas, river-like
230 pattern of denser crazes with no smooth region,
indicating a typical rough feature, which is
considered from a large number of interfaces
introduced by GO (more than 0.2% in Fig. 3c). On
the contrary, more stepladder-like area appears on
the fracture surface of PMG/epoxy (Fig. 3g)
indicating weak interface between PMG and resin,
so that crazes occur to be propagating along

different surfaces of PMG. From Fig. d and h we can
see a distinct difference in the interfacial interactions
between the epoxy matrix and the nanoplatelets.
This observed phenomenon proves that the
nanoplatelets reinforcing composites strongly
depend on the interaction, GO can prevent cracks
from propagating in epoxy matrix nanocomposites
and PMG cannot. And as a result, epoxy is
toughened by GO and not reinforced by PMG.

240 We suggest that two main differences between GO
and PMG lead to these results. First, GO bears a
large amount of hydroxyl, carboxyl and epoxy
functional groups, the two former groups can
provide mechanical interlocking and hydrogen
bonding for the interaction between resin and GO,
the latter one can also be bonding with the matrix by
reacting with the amino curing agent. These
chemical bonds contributed to the efficient load
transfer between matrix and nanoplatelets, and
250 absorb large amounts of energy to prevent or bridge
the growth of micro-crack in matrix effectively.
Together with the high surface area of GO, this
surface chemistry leads to stronger interfacial
interactions with epoxy and thus substantially larger
influence on the properties of the neat resin. Second,
the existence of polar functional groups on the FGS
surface, as well as the extremely small thickness of
the resulting GO lead to a homogenous dispersion of
nanoplatelets in matrix. This state of dispersion
probably results in a stronger mechanical
interlocking with the polymer chains and,
consequently, better adhesion. All of these factors
contribute to the increase of impact strength. These
strong interfacial interactions enable graphene to
bring its amazing mechanical properties into effect,
achieving toughness of epoxy resin. Moreover, the
chemical bonds between GO and matrix slightly
reduce the crosslink density of epoxy resin, which
also enable the polymer chains to slip and provide
more free volume under impact. In contrast, linking
isocyanate functional groups with GO consume a
certain amount of the hydroxyl groups, which
decreases the hydrogen bonding and introduces
voids into the matrix, the epoxy groups of PMG also
has less linking with matrix because of the steric
hindrance. Insufficient interface bonding cause the
impact strength is lower than that of neat resin by
easier crack propagation along the interface. The
matrix would not be toughened when lacking
280 chemical bonding of resin and nanoplatelets.
Furthermore, when the weight percentage of
nanoplatelet is 0.4%, the maximum impact strength
is obtained, in both GO/epoxy and PMG/epoxy.

285 Maldistribution of graphene in resin may lead to the 335
 decline in impact strength when the loading is higher
 than 0.4%. The performance of PMG/epoxy
 nanocomposite degraded due to agglomeration of
 nanosheets and weak interfacial bond.

290 **3.4 Thermodynamic properties of GO/epoxy and
 PMG/epoxy nanocomposites**

295 The glass transition temperature (T_g) of epoxy
 nanocomposites testing by DMA are shown in Table
 3. It can be seen that the T_g of both GO/epoxy and
 PMG/epoxy nanocomposites decrease with the
 loading of nanoplatelets increasing, and the T_g of
 GO/epoxy nanocomposite is even lower than that of
 300 PMG/epoxy nanocomposite. According to the two
 dimensional structure and high specific surface area,
 graphene nanosheets introduce a large amount of
 interfaces into epoxy matrix, which lead to easier
 movement of polymer chains by declining the cross-
 linked density of matrix and reducing the physical
 cross-linking of the resin segments. When the
 305 temperature increases, polymer chains move directly
 along the plane of graphene with less hindrance. The
 interfaces increase with the increasing of content of
 graphene nanosheets, so the T_g decline with
 increasing mass fraction of graphene nanosheets.
 Moreover, the chemical bonds between GO and
 310 epoxy matrix slightly lower the cross-linking density
 of matrix and increase the free volume, which cause
 the T_g lower than PMG/epoxy composite through
 the relaxing movements of polymer chains.

315 **4 Conclusions**

315 In summary, adding modified graphene, GO can
 enhance the impact strength of nanocomposite
 effectively at a low loading. With the addition of 0.4
 wt% GO nanosheets, the impact strength of
 GO/epoxy nanocomposite exhibited a prominent
 320 increase of 79.4%. The improvement in mechanical
 properties should attribute to the strong interfacial
 bonding between nanoplatelets and matrix, which
 including both chemical and physical bonds. And
 PMG failed to toughen epoxy because of weak
 325 interaction for lacking of strong bonds with epoxy
 matrix. The T_g of GO/epoxy and PMG/epoxy
 nanocomposites are both declined.

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Table 1. The results of XPS analysis

Sample	Atomic Percentage/(%)		
	C	O	N
Graphite	99	1	0
GO	73	27	0
PMG	75	17	8

Table 2. Impact strength of nanocomposites

Sample	Impact strength of samples at different filler loadings /(KJ/m ²)			
	0%	0.2%	0.4%	0.6%
GO/Epoxy	1.75	3.14	3.50	2.55
PMG/Epoxy	1.75	1.16	1.34	0.94

Table 3. Glass transition temperature of nanocomposites

Sample	Glass transition temperature of samples testing by DMTA /(°C)			
	0%	0.2%	0.4%	0.6%
Epoxy	161	-	-	-
GO/Epoxy	161	149	133	116
PMG/Epoxy	161	161	157	148

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Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of GO (a) and PMG (b).

Fig. 1. AFM images of GO after ultrasonic exfoliation in water (a), THF (b).

Fig.3. FESEM images of fracture surface after Izod impact strength test: (a) and (b) neat resin; GO /epoxy nanocomposites at (c)0.2wt.%, (d) 0.4wt.% and (e), (f) 0.6wt.%; PMG/epoxy nanocomposites at (g)0.2wt.%, (h) 0.4wt.%, and (i),(j) 0.6wt.%

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